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STRESS MANAGEMENT IN BANKING: A CONCERN FOR EMPLOYEE BURNOUT

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ABSTRACT

Today workplace stress is becoming a matter of concern for all the organizations. Banking sector is no more an exception. Workplace stress has emerged as a black plague in this present scenario. In India, banks are amongst top ten stressed work places. Despite of feeling relaxed with the advent of modern technology and innovations in the banking sector, employees are feeling overloaded with work and stressed out. With the advancement in technology, banks have to make rapid changes. It has become hard for employees to cope with these changes. And the result is stress. An attempt has been made to study the causes and effects of stress amongst bank employees. The ways to manage stress has also been suggested. Measures to overcome stress that affects the physical and mental well being of employees are also suggested in the paper.

Key words: Stress Management, Banking, Employee Burnout

1. INTRODUCTION

Stress has become a pervading issue of everyone's life in this modern world. The modern world which is often regarded as a world of achievements has become a world of stress. Be it family, any social activity or any business organization, stress is everywhere. Right from birth till death, an individual is invariably exposed to various stressful situations. Our economy has shown growth in almost all sectors, but stress has also joined hands with this growth. Individuals under stress are experiencing various psychosomatic and psychological disorders, the feelings of frustration, dissatisfaction with life in general. Workplace stress is the harmful biological reaction that occurs when there is poor match between job profiles and the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. These conditions, ultimately affects the job performance and the health of the individuals. But a little amount of stress may prove to be healthy for an organization. Stress can be positive as well as negative.

Various studies have depicted that stress is increasing at a rising rate in the Banking sector. Due to recession in the global market and cut-throat competition, banks are facing many challenges. As a response of which, they have to make efforts to increase their efficiency. Banks, these days, are restructuring themselves. This results in more workload on their employees.

Organization stress ultimately results in employee turnover, changes in employee's behavior and attitude. A little organization stress is healthy as it increases the efficiency. But stress beyond limits destroys the inner peace of the employees and ultimately hampers the growth of the individual as well as the organization.

Effective stress management can be done at the individual level as well as at the organizational level in various ways. Stress management can be divided into two phases: the first is coping with stress and the second is facing the stress with the help of relaxation techniques such as meditation. As every individual is different, psychotherapies should be used. Banks should treat people at work differently, treating them with respect and valuing their efforts. Banks should introduce Employee Assistance Programmes (EAPs) and stress control workshops according to the level of employees as level of stress and employees are directly related. If psychological wellness and health of the employees are improved, productivity shall also increase. Because it is said that, "A Healthy Employee is a Productive Employee"

2. OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of this research paper are as follows-

1. To study the causes of stress among employees.
2. To study the effect of stress on productivity of the organization.
3. To study the effectiveness of stress management programmes.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Stevenson, Anne and Harper, Sarah (2006), investigated the possible effects of workplace stress in academics on the student learning experience at Scottish Higher Education Institute. For their study, he collected primary data by framing a questionnaire. The questionnaire covered the background information, general attitudes, support from colleagues, perceived stress levels, perceived stressors, and perceived effects of stress and positive aspects of stress. For their analysis, he used the statistical package for social scientists where frequencies, cross-tabulations and tests for significance were calculated. Qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis. For their study, he conducted this survey in 1994 and for the follow up the same survey was repeated in 2003. They found significant changes in a decade. They concluded that stress had positive as well as negative impact on the student learning experience.

Joshi, Vijay and Goyal, K.A. (2012), made an effort to study stress management among bank employees with reference to mergers and acquisitions. The study focused on the identification of various stressors that increases the level of stress among employees. The stressors which were identified in the study were uncertainty, insecurity, fears concerning job loss, job changes, compensation, changes in power, status, prestige, workload, working hours, technological problem at work, inadequate salary, time for family job worries at home group

differences and communication. The findings suggested that employees satisfaction should be the first priority of banks so that desired targets can be achieved.

Garg, Rachita and Shukla, Harish (2013), attempted to study the reasons of stress among the bank employees and the ways used by employees to cope with the stress generated at workplace. They used primary as well as secondary data for their study. They found that majority of employees in banks are stressed. The stressed employees also try to find a solution to relieve them from stress. They suggested various strategies such as encouraging and appreciating employees, job rotation, job enrichment, decentralization, cracking jokes, playing games, guidance and counseling, quality consciousness awareness programs, psychological support and many more to minimize stress. They also suggested five day week working so that the employees can get more time for themselves and their family and discharge other social responsibilities.

4. STRESSORS

Individual level Stressors	Group level Stressors	Organizational level Stressors
Career changes	Managerial behaviour	Organizational climate
Career concerns	Lack of group cohesiveness	Organizational structure
Role ambiguity	Lack of participation in decision making	Organizational leadership
Role conflict	Workforce violence	Organizational changes
Personality	Sexual harassment	Workload

5. EFFECT OF STRESS

Excessive stress proves to be harmful for an individual. It ultimately leads to compromised health and loss of productivity. Absenteeism, shirking work responsibilities, arriving late, leaving early, etc., loss of productivity, increase in employee turnover ,more of error prone work, memory loss, etc., cribbing, various psychological and psychometric problems, over-reacting, arguing, getting irritated, frustration, suicides, deteriorating health, more of accidents, etc., eating disorders, excessive smoking and drinking, insomnias , depression, improper work, delay in completion of job etc.

6. STRESS MANAGEMENT PROGRAMMES

Banks are amongst the top ten stressed workplaces in India. To increase the productivity and efficiency of the banks, banks have come forward with a number of solutions. Banks are employing Human Resource practitioners to solve these issues. Human Resource Department has become an integral part of Bank. Human Resource Practitioners are being involved in planning decisions. Banks are implementing various strategies at all the levels so that workplace stress can be eliminated.

- 1.) Employees health is being given priority over other things
- 2.) Effective communication strategy is a tool through which the effect of most of the stressors like uncertainty, insecurity and fear of job loss can be eliminated.
- 3.) Employees are being reassessed after accomplishment of every task
- 4.) It has been proposed that Employee Development Programmes should be conducted from the initial stage so that employees can easily understand the working environment.
- 5.) Stress Control Workshops are being conducted by Banks according to the level of employees.
- 6.) Stress in banking sector is mostly due to excess work pressure and work life

7. SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1.) Job roles need to be identified to eliminate role ambiguity.
- 2.) Employees grievances must be handled carefully so that they can mingle up in the working culture of the organization. It is important from the point of view of organizational objectives as we all know that only a satisfied employee is capable of satisfying the customer and customer's satisfaction is the priority of any organization.
- 3.) Psychiatrists should be employed so that stress audit can be conducted at all levels in the organization and stress prone areas can be identified. Thus, improving conditions of job and alleviating job stress

8. WAYS OF REDUCING AND MANAGING STRESS

A feeling of control and a healthy balance in your schedule is a necessary part of managing stress. Learning how to manage your responsibilities, accomplish your goals and still have time for rest and relaxation requires that you practice time management skills. Try setting a specific goal for yourself that will improve your mood and help you reduce stress. Start by filling out a goal-setting worksheet.

Avoid procrastination. Putting off assignments or responsibilities until the last minute can create more mental and physical stress than staying on top of them. Procrastination can affect many aspects of daily life, such as the quality of your work, the quality of your sleep, and your mood. Exercise regularly. Physical activity can help you burn off the energy generated by stress. Practice to ensure that you are well-rested. Sleep deprivation can cause many physical and mental problems and can increase stress. Try mindfulness meditation. Limit (or eliminate) the use of stimulants like caffeine, which can elevate the stress response in your body. Pace yourself throughout the day, taking regular breaks from work or other structured activities. During breaks from class, studying, or work, spend time walking outdoors, listen to music or just sit quietly, to clear and calm your mind. Start a journal. Many people find journaling to be helpful for managing stress, understanding emotions, and making decisions and changes in their lives.

Realize that we all have limits. Learn to work within your limits and set realistic expectations for yourself and others. Recognize the role your own thoughts can play in causing you distress. Challenge beliefs you may hold about yourself and your situation that may not be accurate. For example, do you continuously fall short of what you think you “should” accomplish? When our minds continuously feed us messages about what we “should” achieve, “ought” to be, or “mustn’t” do, we are setting ourselves up to fall short of goals that may be unrealistic, and to experience stress along the way. Learn techniques for replacing unrealistic thoughts with more realistic ones. Find humor in your life. Laughter can be a great tension-reducer. Seek the support of friends and family when you need to “vent” about situations that bring on stressful feelings. But make sure that you don’t focus exclusively on negative experiences; try to also think of at least three things that are going well for you, and share those experiences.

Try setting a specific goal for yourself that will improve your mood and help you reduce stress. Start by filling out a goal-setting worksheet then help yourself stay on track by using your weekly motivator worksheet.

9. CONCLUSION

The efficiency of the workforce is the most decisive factor in the growth of any industry. Efficiency of a workforce is interdependent with the health and inner peace of an employee. Giving more importance to work and less importance to health and family is the main cause behind this workplace stress.

Stress, in the present scenario has become a deep rooted evil which needs to be uprooted. Stress itself is a problem which in turn gives birth to a number of problems. There is a dire need of stress management programmes to relief stress and to reduce its harmful effects .This article is an effort to study the need of Stress Management Programmes due to increasing dangers of stress under which it becomes difficult for an employee to work. Through various studies, it has been found that those firms which have adopted stress management strategies have gained a competitive edge over other firms as their employees work more efficiently.

9. References

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